

RECYCLING OF THERMOSET COMPOSITES BY MICROWAVE PYROLYSIS

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ABSTRACT

A scrap blade from a wind turbine was microwave pyrolysed. The recovered glass fibres were characterised by SEM and TGA. The possibility to use the fibres to prepare new composites were evaluated. Laminates were prepared where fibres mats with virgin and recovered glass fibres were altered. Mechanical testing showed that it is possible to prepare composite with up to 35 wt.-% recovered fibre without losing too much of the mechanical properties.

INTRODUCTION

Thermoset composites are versatile materials and used for a wide range of industrial applications, such as boats, automotive components and wind turbine blades.

Thermoset composites are however, relatively difficult to recycle and no system to recycle thermoset composites has been established yet. Thus, scrap composites often end up on landfill sites. There are several reasons why thermoset composites are difficult to recycle. In contrast to thermoplastic composites, the matrix in the thermoset composite is cross-linked and cannot be reprocessed. Further, composites are complex materials consisting of a polymer matrix, a fibre reinforcement and in many cases also fillers and core materials.

Several methods to recycle thermoset composites have been evaluated. One of the most straight forward methods is to grind the composites and to use the recyclate as filler in virgin composites or in plastics. This has been demonstrated in several studies [1-3]. The recyclate could for example be used as a filler for thermoplastic polymers. A difficulty with this method is that the recyclate must be able to compete with existing fillers on the

market. Fillers like calcium carbonate are very cheap and this has hampered the commercialization of this recycling technique [4, 5].

Another possibility to recycle composites is to incinerate the polymer matrix and to recover the energy [6]. However, composites often have a very high inorganic content. Thus, the energy content is very low, which limits the usefulness of this method.

In the present study the possibility to recycle thermoset composite by microwave pyrolysis has been evaluated. Microwave pyrolysis is a relatively new method where the material is heated by microwaves in an inert atmosphere. Thus, the polymer matrix is degraded into gas and oil, while the inorganic fibres are recovered. Heating with microwaves has the potential of saving energy in comparison to conventional heating techniques. Microwave pyrolysis is presently not well studied but the possibility to recover carbon fibres by microwave pyrolysis was studied by Lester et al. [7]. The microwave pyrolysis has also been studied for the recycling of plastic wastes [8].

In this study we have recycled glass fibre composites by means of microwave pyrolysis. A blade from a wind turbine was used as a research object. The wing was cut into small pieces and pyrolysed. The oil from the pyrolysis process was characterized by gas chromatography-mass spectroscopy (GC-MS). The recovered fibres were characterized by scanning electron microscopy (SEM) and thermogravimetric analysis (TGA). The possibility to use the recovered fibres to prepare new composites was evaluated. Non-woven fibre mats were prepared from the recovered glass fibres. Laminates were prepared by alternating lay-up of the mats with recovered fibres with a commercial glass fibre mat at various ratios. The laminates were cured

by compression moulding and the mechanical properties of the resulting composites were evaluated.

EXPERIMENTAL

A scrap wing from a wind craft mill was cut into about 15 cm long pieces and placed in a jar, transparent to microwave radiation. The jar was applied in a 1-litre reactor equipped with a magnetron of 1 kW and the samples were pyrolysed at 450°C for 1 hour. The oil form from the pyrolysis was collected and analysed with gas chromatography mass spectrometry (GC-MC) and with bomb calorimetry (ASTM D 4809).

The recovered glass fibres were characterized by thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) using a Q500 from TA Instruments. Samples, typical 20 mg, were heated 10°C per minute in an atmosphere of oxygen.

Composites were prepared from the recovered glass fibres. The fibres were first treated in a ball mill for 30 minutes in order to separate the fibres. This created a fluffy material. Non-woven glass fibre mats were prepared by manually blending the recovered fibres with 15 wt.-% of a bicomponent fibre (Eastlon PET, 4.4 dtex, from Far Eastern Industries Ltd.). The fibres were then fed from top of a cylinder. A vacuum was applied in the bottom of the cylinder. When feeding the fibres from the top they slowly fell down against a filter installed at the bottom of the cylinder. The fibres were then transferred to a compression moulding machine and processed at 130°C, 0.1 MPa for 4 minutes. Thus, non-woven fibre mats with a random orientation were formed. The fibre mats were impregnated by hand lay-up using an unsaturated polyester resin (Reichhold 31660-02) using 2 wt.-% tert-butyl bensoyl peroxide (Syrgis Performance Initiators). The composites were prepared by alternating mats with recovered fibres with virgin glass fibre mats (non-woven mats, 300 g/m²). The composites were cured at 170°C, 70 kPa for 8 minutes.

The Charpy impact strength was evaluated in accordance with ISO 179 using a Zwick test instrument. The un-notched specimens were tested edge wise. The flexural properties of the prepared composites were evaluated with a tensile testing machine, H10K from Tinius Olsen, according to ISO 14125.

RESULTS

The recovered fibres from the pyrolysis were characterized with SEM and an example is shown in Figure 1. As it can be seen from the micrograph, the fibres are coated with a pyrolysis char showing that the resin is not completely degraded.

Fig. 1. SEM micrograph of the recovered glass fibre.

The recovered fibres were also characterized with TGA, see Figure 2. This analysis showed that there are still 2.2 wt.-% organic materials that were not degraded during the pyrolysis.

The result of the flexural testing is shown in Figure 3. As can be seen, the composite with only recovered fibres has very poor mechanical properties. This can be caused by several factors. First, the surface properties of the glass fibres being altered will influence the mechanical properties. The SEM showed that the surface of the fibres was covered by a char.

Fig 2. Thermogravimetric analysis of the recovered glass fibres.

Thus, there will be poor adhesion between the sizing of the fibre and the matrix.

Fig. 3. The flexural strength for composites prepared with 100 wt.-% virgin fibres down to 0 wt.-% virgin fibres. The error bars shows plus minus one standard deviation.

Secondly, agglomerations of the recovered fibre in the prepared non-woven mats can act as stress inducers. Figure 4 shows the flexural modulus from the same testing. It follows the same pattern with very low mechanical properties for the composite consisting only of recovered fibres. However, the test shows that it is possible to use up to 35 wt.-% recovered fibres without losing too much of the mechanical properties. Such a composite could be used for some application where lower mechanical properties are sufficient.

Fig. 4. Flexural modulus for composites prepared with 100 wt.-% virgin fibres down to 0 wt.-% virgin fibres.

The impact strength of the composites is shown in Figure 5. The non-woven fibre mats prepared from recovered fibres consists of relatively short fibres

and the impact strength of these composites is clearly lower in comparison to the composites prepared from only virgin fibres. However, test also shows that the composites which contained both virgin and recovered fibres had relatively good impact properties.

Fig 5. Impact strength for composites prepared with 100 wt.-% virgin fibres down to 0 wt.-% virgin fibres.

The cross-section of the composites were characterized with SEM. An example of a micrograph from the composite prepared from 100 wt.-% recycled fibres are shown in Figure 6. Some voids can be seen where only the resin is present. The lower mechanical properties for the composites prepared from recycled fibres can be explained by the surface of the fibres being altered, not giving good adhesion between the fibres and the matrix. Irregularities in the non-woven fibre mats will also contribute to the mechanical properties. Voids and coarse fibre agglomerations can act as stress inducers and thereby decrease the mechanical performance.

Figure 6. SEM micrograph of the composite with 100 wt.-% recycled fibres.

The pyrolysis oil was characterized by GC-MS and bomb calorimetry. The pyrolysis oil had a relatively high calorimetric energy content, 34.5 MJ/kg. The energy content is almost comparable to a petroleum based oil. The largest peaks in the chromatogram were identified and are presented in Table 1.

Table 1. GC-MS analysis of the pyrolysis oil.

No.	Compound
1	Styrene
2	Toluene
3	Benzene, 1,1'-(1,3-propanediyl)bis-
4	Alfa-methylstyrene
5	Ethylbenzene
6	Benzene
7	Naphthalene

The oil contains mainly of aromatic compounds, and it is very different compared to a commercial petroleum based oil. The high content of aromatic components can limit the usage of the oil.

Conclusions

Microwave pyrolysis was used to recover glass fibres from a scrap wing blade from a wind turbine. The pyrolysis will generate gas, oil and recovered glass fibres. The pyrolysis oil had a relatively high calorific energy content and consists of various aromatic compounds. The oil could eventually used as a fuel or be converted to synthesis gas. The recovered fibres were characterised with SEM, and the micrographs showed that the fibres are covered with a char which has not been degraded after the pyrolysis. The recovered glass fibres were used to prepare new thermoset composites. Laminates, consisting of both recycled fibres and virgin fibres, were therefore prepared. The mechanical tests of these composites indicate that it is possible to produce composites with roughly 15-35 wt.-% recycled fibres with relatively good mechanical properties.

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